

The Diagnostic Yield and Safety of Pleuroscopy in Evaluation of Lymphocytic Exudative Pleural Effusion: A Single Center Study

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Abstract

Background: Diagnosis of lymphocytic exudative pleural effusion is challenging, where significant part of cases remain undiagnosed despite pleural fluid analysis, microbiological and radiological evaluation. Pleural biopsy is often needed to determine the causes. Pleuroscopy permits direct inspection of pleural cavity and targeted biopsy and thus increasing diagnostic yield. This study aimed to evaluate diagnostic yield of pleuroscopy and its safety in lymphocytic exudative pleural effusion.

Methods: Current study is descriptive retrospective and prospective study, conducted in Babylon/Iraq between April 2022 and September 2025 on 50 adult patients who underwent pleuroscopy to evaluate lymphocytic exudative pleural effusion which remained undiagnosed despite cytological, microbiological, biochemical and radiological investigations. The study recorded and analyzed the demographic data, clinical features, imaging findings, pleuroscopical findings, histopathological diagnosis and procedure-related complications.

Results: The mean age was 56.1 ± 16.5 years with predominance of male (66%). Shortness of breath was the most common symptom (94%) followed by cough (82%). Unilateral pleural effusion was predominant (86%). Pleuroscopy demonstrated pleural nodules or masses in 74% of cases and erythematous/inflamed in 20%. Pleural tissue was sufficient for histopathological diagnosis in all patients. Histopathological examination showed malignancy in 42%, infection in 42%, non-specific pleuritis in 10% and non-conclusive in 6%. The diagnostic yield was 94% with no significant procedure-related complications.

Conclusion: Current study showed that pleuroscopy had a high diagnostic yield and a high safety profile in evaluation of lymphocytic exudative pleural effusion. The malignancy and infection constituted the majority of the final diagnosis of lymphocytic exudative pleural effusion.

Introduction

Pleural effusion is an abnormal collection of fluid within the pleural space. In healthy people, pleural fluid is produced from circulation of parietal pleura in a continuous process, in the same time is reabsorbed by lymphatic system (stomata) in parietal pleura, the main function of pleural fluid is to give lubrication and allow smooth movement of the lungs during respiration [1-3]. The normal amount of pleural fluid is small (about 10-15 mL), concentration of protein is low (less than 1.5

g/dL), the count of total white blood cells is (1.716×10^3) cells/mL [3]. Differential cell count consists of: 75% macrophages, 23% lymphocytes, and minor present mesothelial cells (1% to 2%), neutrophils (1%) and eosinophils (0%) [3]. Regarding neutrophil count is slightly more elevated in smokers than non-smokers [3].

The abnormal accumulation of fluid in the pleural cavity occurs when the production of pleural fluid becomes greater than its reabsorption [3]. Exudative pleural

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Keywords:

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effusion forms when a filtration process exceeds the maximum lymph flow due to an increase in permeability of the systemic capillaries to protein, this would lead to an increase in pleural fluid protein concentration, in general exudative pleural effusions are caused by infections such as pneumonia, malignancy, tuberculosis, collagen vascular diseases, and other inflammatory conditions [3]. Transudative pleural effusion forms when a filtration process exceeds the reabsorption process due to an increase in capillary and mesothelial water permeability, in addition to increased hydrostatic pressure, occurs in congestive heart failure, cirrhosis, nephrotic syndrome and malnutrition [3]. Pleural disease affects more than 300 per 100,000 individuals of population per annum, worldwide [4]. In the United States alone, 1.5 million diagnosed with pleural effusion pleural effusions annually, pulmonologists diagnosed around a quarter of diagnoses [4]. Despite the history, physical exam and pleural fluid analysis will lead to the diagnosis in the most of the cases, around 26% of pleural effusions cannot be diagnosed and further work-up is needed [2]. Many of undiagnosed effusions are exudative, the most common cause either malignancy or tuberculosis according to TB prevalence regions, where in low tuberculosis (TB) prevalence areas, malignancy consists of more than 50% of undiagnosed exudative pleural effusion, in TB endemic areas, pleural tuberculosis consists of 84.5% of undiagnosed exudative pleural effusions, in addition to other causes such as sarcoidosis and rheumatoid arthritis [5].

The first step in the assessment of a pleural effusion is determining the type of pleural effusion, transudate or exudate, the principal method to make this differentiation is still Light's criteria by using protein and lactate dehydrogenase levels both in the pleural fluid and blood [6,7]. Light's criteria is defined by the following:

- 1- Pleural fluid protein/ serum protein >0.5,
- 2- Pleural fluid lactate dehydrogenase (LDH)/ serum LDH >0.6,
- 3- Pleural fluid LDH greater than two third of the upper limit of serum LDH [8].

To diagnose exudative pleural effusion, the effusion should meet at least one of the criteria, Light's criteria correctly diagnoses more than 95% of exudates, but some cases of transudative effusion may misclassify as exudative (pseudoexudative), particularly in heart failure patients treated with diuretics [8]. In these patients measuring serum-pleural albumin gradient > 1.2 g/dl and low pleural fluid cholesterol less than 45 mg/dl support a transudative effusion [8]. Thus, the other components of the fluid analysis, including routine biochemical and cytological examination, are crucial and can further increase diagnostic accuracy [7].

Cell counts and differential are beneficial in evaluation of the underlying cause of a pleural effusion and are routinely performed, the mechanism of pleural injury and the duration of effusion can be associated with predominance of particular line of WBC [8]. A lymphocyte predominant exudative effusion (lymphocytes >50% of the whole WBC) is often time associated with chronic pleural process such as TB, malignancy, RA, while neutrophilic predominance (> 50%) is mostly seen in acute reaction such as pneumonia, empyema, PE (early phase) [8]. Conditions associated with grossly bloody pleural effusion include malignancy, pulmonary infarction, and trauma, elevated eosinophil count (>10% of the WBC count) are usually seen in pneumothorax and hemothorax [8,9]. While pleural fluid analysis and radiological investigations can be used to diagnose the majority of pleural effusion, about 25% of pleural effusion cases remain undiagnosed and would need pleural biopsy for making a diagnosis [10]. Different modalities such as closed pleural biopsy, CT or Ultrasound guided biopsy or pleuroscopically guided biopsy are used for pleural biopsy, closed pleural biopsy has poor sensitivity in the diagnosis, where it is inconclusive in about 10-27% of cases [11]. Due to this high percentage of undiagnosed pleural effusion despite extensive testing, pleuroscopy emerges as a valuable tool that permits direct visualization and targeted biopsies and potentially improves diagnostic accuracy. Current study aimed to evaluate diagnostic yield and safety of pleuroscopy in patients with lymphocytic exudative pleural effusion.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Patients

This descriptive retrospective and prospective study was conducted in Babylon/Iraq between April 2022 and September 2025 on 50 adult patients who underwent pleuroscopy for evaluation of lymphocytic exudative pleural effusion after obtaining approval from the Institutional Ethic Committee of Al-marjan teaching hospital/Babylon center for internal medicine – Iraqi board for medical specialization

Inclusion Criteria

1. The patients aged above 15 years
2. Underwent pleuroscopy
3. The pleural effusion is exudative (described as exudative by Light's criteria) and have lymphocyte count > 30% on pleural fluid differential count
4. Cytological, microbiological, biochemical and imaging tests failed to diagnose.

Exclusion Criteria

1. The age below 15 years
2. Patient refusal
3. Unfitting patients

Data of Patients

Data of 50 cases fulfilling inclusion criteria were retrieved from the patients medical reports which include :

1. Socio-demographic data (Age, gender, smoking).
2. Clinical data: Symptoms such as (dyspnea, cough, chest pain, hemoptysis, fever, weight loss), history of TB contact, asbestos exposure and family history of malignancy.
3. Chest CT findings data: laterality of effusion, pleural thickening and nodularity, parenchymal consolidation or masses.
4. Pleuroscopic data: appearance of pleura surface (nodules or masses, erythema, normal), pleural fluid appearance (purulent, bloody), anatomical distribution of lesions and significant procedure related complications.
5. Histopathological data: include malignancy, infection, non-specific pleuritis and non-conclusive.

Procedure

All procedures performed by pulmonologists. Written consent taken from all patients. Pleuroscopy done under LA or GA. The option of anesthesia was left to the patients. The patients was placed in lateral decubitus with affected side up. Vital parameters, ECG monitoring, blood pressure, and oxygen saturation by pulse oximetry were monitored. After sterilization of skin, small incision (1-2 cm) is made with scalpel in the mid-axillary line (4th-6th intercostal space), followed by dissection of intercostal muscles with blunt until reaching to the pleural space. Disposable trocar with inner diameter of 8 mm is inserted, followed by the insertion of the semi-rigid pleuroscope(Olympus BF-160, outer diameter 7mm and channel 2.8mm) through the trocar, the pleural fluid aspirated with systematic inspection of pleural cavity. Pleural biopsy samples (usually 3-4) were taken with biopsy forceps, particularly abnormal appearance site. Chest tube (24F) was placed in the same port and connected to the underwater seal, typically removed in the next day, after good lung expansion and minimal fluid drainage.

Results

Socio-Demographic Data

The mean age was 56.1 ± 16.5 years, with predominance of male (66%). 40% of patients were smokers, while a positive family history of malignancy was reported in 28%. Asbestos exposure in 16% and contact with tuberculosis in 20%. (Table 1)

Table 1: Description of the Socio-Demographic and Exposure Status of the Patients

Characteristic	N = 50 ¹
Age, years	56.1 ± 16.5
Sex	
Male	33 (66.0%)
Female	17 (34.0%)

Smoking	20 (40.0%)
Positive family history of malignancy	14 (28.0%)
Asbestos exposure	8 (16.0%)
Contact with tuberculosis case	10 (20.0%)

Note: ¹Mean ± SD; n (%)

Symptoms and Signs Data

Dyspnea was the most frequent symptom (94%) followed by cough (82%) then chest pain (36%) and hemoptysis (18%) . Systemic symptoms involved fever and weight loss were presented in 50% and 46% of patients respectively. (Table 2)

Table 2: Description of the Signs and Symptoms Experienced by the Patients

Characteristic	N = 50 ¹
Respiratory features	
Shortness of the breath	47 (94.0%)
Cough	41 (82.0%)
Chest pain	18 (36.0%)
Hemoptysis	9 (18.0%)
Systemic features	
Fever	25 (50.0%)
Weight loss	23 (46.0%)

Note: ¹n (%)

Chest CT Findings Data

Chest CT showed unilateral effusion in 86%, consolidation in 68% and masses or nodules in 32%, while pleural nodularity in 16% and pleural thickening in 12%. (Table 3)

Table 3: Description of the Chest CT Findings in the Study Cohort

Characteristic	N = 50 ¹
Pleural effusion laterality	
Unilateral effusion	43 (86.0%)
Bilateral effusion	7 (14.0%)
Pleura abnormalities	
Thickened pleura	6 (12.0%)
Pleural nodularity	8 (16.0%)
Pulmonary parenchymal lesions	
Consolidation	34 (68.0%)
Mass or nodule	16 (32.0%)

Note: ¹ n (%)

Pleuroscopic Findings and Pleural Fluid Characteristics Data

A pleural mass or nodule was observed in 74% of patients, while diffuse erythematous or inflamed pleura was seen in 20%, normal pleural surface was noted in 8.0%. Pleural fluid was purulent in 50%, bloody effusion in 26% and others in 24%. (Table 4)

Table 4: Pleuroscopic Findings and Pleural Fluid Characteristics (N = 50)

Characteristic	N = 50 ¹
Pleural surface appearance	
Pleural mass or nodule	37 (74.0%)
Diffuse erythematous / inflamed pleura	10 (20.0%)
Other pleura findings	18 (36.0%)
Normal pleura	4 (8.0%)
Pleural fluid appearance	
Purulent fluid	25 (50.0%)
Bloody fluid	13 (26.0%)
Others (serous, clear)	12 (24.0%)

Note: ¹ n (%)

Biopsy Adequacy, Anesthetic Technique, and Histopathological Diagnosis Data

Tissue biopsy was sufficient for histopathological diagnosis in all procedures (100%). General anesthesia was the predominant, used in 84.0% of cases, while local anesthesia was in 16%. Histopathological examination revealed that infection and malignancy were equally common, 42% for each. Non-specific pleuritis was identified in 10%, while only 6% were non-conclusive. (Table 5)

Table 5: Biopsy Adequacy, Anesthetic Technique, and Histopathological Diagnosis

Characteristic	N = 50 ¹
Biopsy adequacy	
Sufficient tissue obtained for diagnosis	50 (100.0%)
Type of anesthesia used for pleuroscopy	
General anesthesia	42 (84.0%)
Local anesthesia	8 (16.0%)
Histopathological diagnosis	
Infection	21 (42.0%)
Malignancy	21 (42.0%)
Non specific pleuritis	5 (10.0%)
Non conclusive	3 (6.0%)

Note: ¹ n (%)

Procedure-Related Complications

None of the 50 patients experienced procedure-related complications such as lung injury, significant bleeding from the chest wall, re-expansion pulmonary edema or procedure-related mortality. (Table 6)

Table 6: Procedure-Related Complications of Pleuroscopy in Patients with Lymphocytic Exudative Pleural Effusion (N = 50)

Characteristic	N = 50 ¹
Lung injury	
Non reported	50 (100.0%)
Significant bleeding chest wall or pleura	

Non reported	50 (100.0%)
Re-expansion pulmonary edema	
Non reported	50 (100.0%)
Procedure related mortality	
Non reported	50 (100.0%)

Note: ¹ n (%)

Discussion

The current study demonstrated that pleuroscopy had diagnostic yield of 94% and was non-conclusive in 3 patients (6%) which is higher than in Naik GP et al. study which reported diagnostic yield about 66.1%, this low rate may be due to high presence of dense adhesion which wasn't presented in current study and also because it didn't considered non-specific pleuritis as definitive diagnosis [12]. The diagnostic yield of this study is approximately similar to the diagnostic yield in studies that involve exudative pleural effusion not only lymphocytic type, where Marwah V et al. and Dermawan JKT et al. reported diagnostic yield of 95.6% and 93.6% respectively [13-14].

In this study, The most common causes of lymphocytic pleural effusion were malignancy in 21 patients (42%) and infection in 21 patients (42%) and this consistent to Christopher DJ et al. which reported infection (tuberculosis) in 47% and malignancy in 43% [15]. Also, Naik GP et al. compatible with current study but with slightly lower rate, where it reported infection (tuberculosis) in 22(35.5%) and malignancy in 18(29%) [12].

In the current study, non-specific pleuritis reported in 10% which is slightly less than reported in other studies, where Naik GP et al. and Patil CB et al. reported non-specific pleuritis in 35.5% and 14.7% respectively [12,16]. Sadaf S et al. reported non-specific pleuritis in 9.5% which is similar to the current study [17]. Non-specific pleuritis needs careful follow up due to the minority of cases have risk of underlying malignancy especially mesothelioma which may developed later [18-20].

In the current study, the mean age was 56.1 ± 16.5 years and the patients were mostly males 33 (66.0%) and female 17 (34%) which is in line with Sadaf S et al. and Naik GP et al [12,17].

In this study, the dyspnea was the main symptom (94%), the cough followed it in about 82%, which also observed in Naik GP et al., Patil et al and Abdelaziz A et al. studies [12,16,21]. In addition, systemic symptoms were common in this study, where fever in 50% and weight loss 46% which also observed in Kumar H et al. but with some differences, where fever in 15% and weight loss in 57% [22].

Regarding CT findings in current study were unilateral pleural effusion in 86%, bilateral effusion in 14%, consolidation in 68%, parenchymal mass and nodules in 32% and pleural nodularity in 16%, this is goes along

with Wu YB al et. study which showed unilateral effusion in 82.5%, bilateral effusion in 17.5%, consolidation in 46.2%, pulmonary mass and nodules in 39.2% and pleural nodularity in 14.9% [23].

In this study, pleural fluid appearance was purulent in 25 patient (50%) and bloody in 13 patients (26%) and this in agreement with Abdelaziz A al et. study in Egypt, where the appearance of pleural effusion was purulent in 38 patients (62.3%) followed by bloody appearance in 23 patients (37.7%) [21].

In this study, the most common finding on pleuroscopy was pleural nodules and masses in 37 patients (74%) and which is associated with final diagnosis of malignancy in majority of patients and this compatible to Abdelaziz A al et., Kumar H al et. and Singh R al et. studies, where showed pleural nodules and masses in (73.8%), (55.5%) and (63%) respectively [21,22,24]. But, in current study, the second most common finding was erythematous and inflamed pleura in 20%, while in Abdelaziz A al et. and Kumar H al et. , pleural thickening and adhesion were the second most common pleuroscopical findings [21,22]. In addition, this study showed normal pleura in 8% and this consistent with study in India, Singh R al et. where normal pleura in 4.6% [24].

In the current study, lesions are distributed mainly in anterior and posterior lower zones (78%) for each, and this appears important in practical implication, where systematic inspection of lower zones may increase rate of lesion detection.

The current study didn't report any significant complications such as re-expansion pulmonary edema, procedure related mortality, significant bleeding from chest wall or pleura and lung injury and this give high safety rate to using of pleuroscopy in diagnosis, which is also reported in Naik GP al et., Marwah V al et. and KS SC al et. studies [12,13,25].

Limitations

Current study had several limitations:

First: Study sample (50) was small, so the results cannot be generalized.

Second: Absence of long-term follow up.

Third: The study was in a single center.

Forth: The study hadn't comparison with other modality such VATs or US guided pleural biopsy.

Conclusion

1. Current study showed that pleuroscopy had a high diagnostic yield and a high safety profile in evaluation of lymphocytic exudative pleural effusion.

2. The malignancy and infection had constituted the majority of the final diagnosis of lymphocytic exudative pleural effusion

Recommendations

1. Early consideration of pleuroscopy in patients with lymphocytic exudative pleural effusion with negative or

indeterminate thoracentesis results to avoid recurrent low yield aspirations.

2. Larger, multicenter studies.

3. Long term follow up of patients with non-specific pleuritis to avoid missing underlying malignancy.

4. Comparison of pleuroscopy with other modality such as US guided pleural biopsy or VAT to assess comparative diagnostic yield and procedure related complications.

References

- [1] Ali MS, Light RW, Maldonado F. Pleuroscopy or video-assisted thoracoscopic surgery for exudative pleural effusion: a comparative overview. *J Thorac Dis.* 2019 Jul;11(7):3207-3216. doi:10.21037/jtd.2019.03.86. PMID:31463153; .
- [2] Kern RM, DePew ZS, Maldonado F. Outpatient thoracoscopy: safety and practical considerations. *Curr Opin Pulm Med.* 2015;21(4):357-362. doi:10.1097/MCP.000000000000168.
- [3] D'Agostino HP, Edens MA. Physiology, Pleural Fluid. [Updated 2023 Aug 28]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan.
- [4] Krishna R, Antoine MH, Alahmadi MH, Rudrappa M. Pleural effusion. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan–. Updated 2024 Aug 31. PMID: 28846252.
- [5] Thomas M, Ibrahim WH, Raza T, et al. Medical thoracoscopy for exudative pleural effusion: an eight-year experience from a country with a young population. *BMC Pulm Med.* 2017;17(1):151. doi:10.1186/s12890-017-0499-y.
- [6] Feller-Kopman DJ, Reddy CB, DeCamp MM, et al. Management of malignant pleural effusions: an official ATS/STS/STR clinical practice guideline. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 2018;198(7):839-849. doi:10.1164/rccm.201807-1415St.
- [7] Li C, Kazzaz FI, Scoon JM, Estrada-Y-Martin RM, Cherian SV. Lymphocyte predominant exudative pleural effusions: a narrative review. *Shanghai Chest.* 2022;6:5.
- [8] Light RW. Pleural effusion and empyema. In: Jameson JL, Fauci AS, Kasper DL, Hauser SL, Longo DL, Loscalzo J, editors. *Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine.* 22nd ed. New York: McGraw Hill; 2025. p. 310-312.
- [9] Sahn SA, Huggins JT, San Jose E, et al. The art of pleural fluid analysis. *Clin Pulm Med.* 2013;20(2):77-96.
- [10] The Role of Medical Thoracoscopy in the Diagnosis of Exudative Lymphocytic Pleural Effusions: An Observational Study. *Monaldi Arch Chest Dis.* 2025 Mar;95(1):3233. doi:10.4081/monaldi.2025.3233.
- [11] Saifullah N, Baig S, Soomro NH, Rizvi N. Exudative pleural biopsies: comparison of diagnostic yield between pleuroscopic and closed percutaneous

pleural biopsies in patients. *Prof Med J*. 2016;23(8):970–974. doi:10.17957/TPMJ/16.3415.

[12] Naik GP, Karanth MPS, Ram A, et al. The role of medical thoracoscopy in the diagnosis of exudative lymphocytic pleural effusions: an observational study. *Monaldi Arch Chest Dis*. 2025; doi:10.4081/monaldi.2025.3233

[13] Marwah V, Bhattacharyya D, Mohamed Ali F, Rajput AK, Sengupta P, Bhati G. Diagnostic utility of medical thoracoscopy in undiagnosed exudative pleural effusions. *Med J Dr DY Patil Vidyapeeth*. 2020 Sep–Oct;13(5):525–528. doi:10.4103/mjdrdypu.mjdrdypu_277_19.

[14] Dermawan JKT, Policarpio-Nicolas ML. Malignancies in pleural, peritoneal, and pericardial effusions. *Arch Pathol Lab Med*. 2020;144(9):1086–1091.

[15] Christopher DJ, Dinakaran S, Gupta R, James P, Isaac B, Thangakunam B. Thoracoscopic pleural biopsy improves yield of Xpert MTB/RIF for diagnosis of pleural tuberculosis. *Respirology*. 2018;23(7):714–717. doi:10.1111/resp.13275. PMID: 29486527.

[16] Patil CB, Dixit R, Gupta R, Gupta N, Indushekar V. Thoracoscopic evaluation of 129 cases having undiagnosed exudative pleural effusions. *Lung India*. 2016;33(5):502–506. doi:10.4103/0970-2113.188969.

[17] Sadaf S, Kazmi S, Noor A, Yasin M, Noor U, Kanwal N. The utility of pleural biopsy in differentiating between different types of lymphocytic exudative pleural effusions. *Pak J Chest Med*. 2021;27(1):32–36.

[18] Reuter SB, Clementsen PF, Bodtger U. Incidence of malignancy and survival in patients with idiopathic pleuritis. *J Thorac Dis*. 2019;11(2):386–392. doi: 10.21037/jtd.2018.12.136.

[19] 1Aujayeb A, Jackson K. A review of the outcomes of rigid medical thoracoscopy in a large UK

district general hospital. *Pleura Peritoneum*. 2020;5(4):20200131. doi: 10.1515/pp-2020-0131.

[20] Deschuyteneer EP, De Keukeleire T. Diagnostic value and safety of thoracoscopic pleural biopsies in pleural exudative effusions of unknown origin, including follow-up. *BMJ Open Respir Res*. 2022;9(1):e001161. doi: 10.1136/bmjresp-2021-001161.

[21] Abdelaziz A, Hassan R, Abdelfattah R, Hassan A, Yehia H, Mady A, Abdelhady E. Validity of pleuroscopy in evaluating pleural effusions of uncertain etiology at the cardiothoracic unit of Minia University Hospital, Egypt. *Cureus*. 2024 Apr 29;16(4):e59300. doi:10.7759/cureus.59300. PMID:38813283; PMCID:PMC11136467.

[22] Kumar H, Arif M, Kumar S, et al. The yield of rigid thoracoscopy in patients of undiagnosed exudative pleural effusion and comparison of pleural fluid and thoracoscopic findings between tuberculosis and malignancy. *Egypt J Bronchol*. 2023;17:60. doi:10.1186/s43168-023-00237-y.

[23] Wu YB, Xu LL, Wang XJ, Wang Z, Zhang J, Tong ZH, Shi HZ. Diagnostic value of medical thoracoscopy in malignant pleural effusion. *BMC Pulm Med*. 2017;17:109. doi:10.1186/s12890-017-0451-1.

[24] Singh R, Shah NZ, Dar KA, Khan U, Gupta N, Verma R. Medical Thoracoscopy: Diagnostic Role in the Management of Undiagnosed Pleural Effusions and Its Complications. *Indian Journal of Chest Diseases and Allied Sciences*. 2022;64(4):258–262.

[25] KS SC, Thimmaiah CM, Hosmane GB. The outcome of medical thoracoscopy in patients with unexplained exudative pleural effusion. *Indian J Respir Care*. 2023;12(2):109–112

